

Management of Islamic Aqedah Based Curriculum at Khoiru Ummah Tahfiz Plus Elementary School

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ABSTRACT: Management of Islamic aqedah based curriculum is implemented by Tahfidz Plus School (STP) SDIT Khoiru Ummah Liwa Lampung Barat. The process of planning, organizing, implementing and supervising the curriculum is implemented as a means of achieving educational goals. This research aims to analyze and describe management of Islamic aqedah based curriculum. This research uses a qualitative descriptive approach with descriptive research type. Data collection techniques use interviews, observation and document study. Data analysis techniques are carried out by collecting data, reducing data, presenting data, and drawing conclusions. The results of this research show that: (1) Planning by formulating the vision, mission, objectives and content of Islamic aqedah curriculum formulated by various authorities. (2) Organizing by compiling an organizational structure and division of tasks, (3) Implementation is carried out by school principals, educators and education staff using learning methods, *talaqiyah fikriyan*, in collaboration with parents and related parties, (4) Supervision is carried out by the school principal and related institutions, and the results of the supervision are utilized to improve the quality of management of Islamic aqedah curriculum.

KEYWORDS: Curriculum, Elementary School, Islamic Aqedah, Management.

INTRODUCTION

Education is an important factor in the existence of a civilization. Education in Islam is always closely related to unity based on aqidah (belief) and is closely related to faith. Education will be delivered to students within the scope of the educational design called the curriculum. The curriculum is an educational plan that summarizes all the learning experiences given to students at school. In a curriculum, philosophy, values, knowledge must be integrated with educational actions (Suhaimi & Rinawati, 2018). Education is also seen as forming the character of individuals who study. Education really needs to pay attention to aspects of character formation of students which are integrated in the curriculum. Based on this, curriculum management is needed to achieve educational goals (Neela & Suriansyah, 2019). A curriculum is a plan to provide a series of learning opportunities to achieve broad and specific goals. The curriculum has an important and strategic role in achieving educational goals. This role is contained in planning, organizing, implementing and evaluating the curriculum.

Factors that can influence the success of curriculum implementation are empowerment in the field of management or curriculum management in the educational institution concerned. Every curriculum designed must reflect the school's vision, mission and goals. It is also important for the curriculum to be innovated, updated and developed from the previous curriculum to be better in the future (Andriyani, Ngadimun & Suriansyah, 2018), because the success of achieving educational goals is determined by the foundation in learning and the elements contained in it, namely the participants students, educators, interaction between students and educators, environment, educational material/content (Salasiah, Asniwati & Effendi, 2018). The government's policy points regarding the curriculum are adjusted to the needs of each school in accordance with the vision and mission of each institution. Curriculum management is the responsibility of each institution concerned. Planning, organizing, implementing and evaluating are very important tasks in implementing learning which are then carried out by teachers in the classroom (Neela & Suriansyah, 2019).

Teachers have a very important role in carrying out learning with students. Some of the functions of teachers in relation to their duties as teachers are teachers as informants, organizers, motivators, directors, initiators, transmitters, facilitators and mediators (Hamalik, 2006). Learning quality is an ability that schools must have in implementing learning effectively and efficiently so as to result in the achievement of predetermined teaching objectives. The components that contribute to its implementation are the teacher's appearance, mastery of the material or curriculum, use of teaching methods, utilization of educational tools or facilities, implementation of learning and evaluation, implementation of curricular and extracurricular activities (Rusman, 2013).

The success of the learning process in an educational institution cannot be separated from the curriculum. The curriculum has a central position in the education process, because the curriculum drives all forms of educational activities to achieve educational goals. The curriculum provides an educational design that functions as a guideline in the education process (Solehuddin, 2022). Apart from the curriculum, the success of an educational institution is also determined by the management of the institution. Management in a broad sense is planning, organizing, directing and controlling organizational resources to achieve the desired goals. An educational institution will run well if there is good management in implementing the curriculum.

Seeing the importance of education, it is necessary to pay serious attention to the concept of education in order to achieve educational goals optimally, in accordance with the goal of Indonesian national education, which is to develop the potential of students to become human beings who have faith and are devoted to God Almighty, with noble character, healthy, knowledgeable, capable, creative, independent and become democratic and responsible citizens.

The importance of curriculum management in efforts to realize national education goals is something that is interesting for researchers to research in more depth. The emergence of many Integrated Islamic Primary Schools (SDIT) today, which implement various curriculum combinations in an effort to provide the best education for the nation's children. The implementation of a curriculum that is unique compared to other schools of the same level makes SDIT an alternative solution for parents to enroll their sons and daughters in receiving basic level education.

The importance of the existence of SDIT which can be an alternative solution to education in Indonesia with independent curriculum management, encouraged the author to conduct research by describing in depth the curriculum management at SDIT so that it can be seen what the desired educational goals, educational materials, teaching processes and evaluations are carried out in form an appropriate learning experience and graduate profile. One of the SDIT schools that has a distinctive curriculum is SDIT Khoiru Ummah or more precisely SDIT Khoiru Ummah Tahfidz Plus School (STP). They have dozens of branches spread across Indonesia, and their experience in curriculum management is very interesting to research.

Through the process of observing the implementation of the current educational curriculum, researchers try to provide an overview of Islamic faith-based curriculum management that is implemented in School Tahfidz Plus (STP) SDIT Khoiru Ummah Liwa, West Lampung. STP-SDIT Khoiru Ummah Liwa, West Lampung is one of the elementary school

(SD) education units located at Jl. Gajah Mada, Pasar Liwa Village, Balik Bukit District, West Lampung Regency, Lampung Province. In carrying out its activities, STP-SDIT Khoiru Ummah Liwa, West Lampung is under the auspices of the Ministry of Education and Culture. STP-SDIT Khoiru Ummah Liwa, West Lampung is a branch of STP-SDIT Khoiru Ummah which is based in Bogor, West Java. Currently STP-SDIT Khoiru Ummah has been established in 16 Provinces, 46 Regencies/Cities and 80 school branches.

Tahfidz Plus Khoiru Ummah School is an educational institution that aspires to give birth Again, the best generation of the people, the generation of Qur'an hafiz, has leadership character, which is reflected in his intelligence in thinking, his knowledge of religion, his courage to voice the truth (Islam), and have a positive impact on their family, community and society. Every level of education in Tahfidz Plus Khoiru Ummah School has a different focus of attention according to level age, development of students' minds and instincts. Combined with the 'talqiyah fikriyan' (building students' ability to think about Islamic and independent solutions), it is hoped that a generation of a generation of Muslims who are ready to become leaders in the future. STP-SDIT Khoiru Ummah Liwa, West Lampung implements an Islamic Creed-based education curriculum which makes the Al-Qur'an and As-Sunnah the main sources of knowledge for students.

Based on interviews conducted with the Principal, the characteristics of STP Khoiru Ummah include: Tahfidz plus school with a curriculum based on Islamic beliefs. The curriculum is prepared independently, all learning material provided is directed at building children's intellectual intelligence and spiritual piety. All learning materials are based on Islamic beliefs. Learning method: talqiyah fikriyan, science is taught in order to improve children's thinking abilities, not just increase their knowledge. Education at school is integrated with education at home. Activities at school and at home follow the Islamic lifestyle. Schools also direct and control students' daily activities at home. Parents act as teachers at home. Teachers at school act like parents during school hours. Parents are in the position of being the first and main teachers for their children. The school will provide knowledge, guidance and direction to parents to become the best teachers for their children.

STP Khoiru Ummah has advantages in the output it produces, namely having an Islamic personality, faqih fiddin, being at the forefront of science and technology and having a leadership spirit. This output is determined based on instructions from the Qur'an

and Sunnah. STP Khoiru Ummah has advantages in curriculum, learning methods and how to handle children. Everything is based on Islamic aqidah. Every learning material taught to children is integrated with Islamic Aqidah. There is no learning material that conflicts with Islamic beliefs. Curriculum management at STP-SDIT Khoiru Ummah is very interesting to know because it has the concept of developing mindsets and attitude patterns for students through the curriculum model applied, namely an Islamic Aqidah-based curriculum.

This research is research related to the implementation of curriculum management based on Islamic beliefs in elementary schools based on Islamic education. The description described above encouraged researchers to conduct research on planning, organizing, implementing and supervising the Islamic faith-based curriculum at STP-SDIT Khoiru Ummah Liwa, West Lampung.

2. RESEARCH METHODS

The main aim of this research is to study how Islamic Aqidah-based curriculum management is implemented by STP SDIT Khoiru Ummah Liwa West Lampung. This research was conducted using a qualitative approach. According to Bogdan and Taylor as quoted by Moloeng, qualitative methods are research procedures that produce descriptive data in the form of written or spoken words from people and observable behavior (Moleong, 2017). Qualitative research is essentially observing people in their environment, interacting with them, trying to understand their language and interpretations of the world around them. For this reason, researchers have to go into the field and be there for quite a long time.

This qualitative research method is often called a naturalistic research method because the research is carried out in natural conditions (Sugiyono, 2008). The type of research used in this research is descriptive qualitative. Descriptive research is research that is used to describe (*to describe*), explain and answer questions about current phenomena and events, both regarding phenomena as they are and analysis of the relationship between various variables in a phenomenon (Arifin, 2012). So descriptive research is research that attempts to describe and interpret existing data, besides that descriptive research is limited to efforts to reveal problems or situations or events as they are, in the nature of simply revealing facts. In this research, the researcher was directly involved as an instrument and collected data for further use described. Researchers carried out research activities on Islamic Aqidah-based curriculum management at STP SDIT Khoiru Ummah Liwa West Lampung and tried to find out about the planning, organization, implementation and evaluation, so that researchers could get an overview of the implementation of curriculum management at STP SDIT Khoiru Ummah Liwa West Lampung.

In research, the data collection step is a stage that determines the process and results of the research to be carried out. Errors in carrying out data collection in a research will have a direct impact on the process and results of a research.

Data collection methods in qualitative research are generally grouped into two types, namely interactive and noninteractive. Interactive methods include interviews and participant observation, while non-interactive methods include non-participant observation, questionnaire techniques, recording documents, and non-participation. There are four types of data collection techniques, namely observation, interviews, documentation and combination or triangulation (Sugiyono, 2012).

Based on the concept above, researchers used data collection techniques by observation, interviews and documentation. However, it is preferred to use in-depth interview techniques because it is better to get the hidden meaning behind existing phenomena.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This research was carried out at the Tahfidz Plus School (STP) SDIT Khoiru Ummah Jl. Gajah Mada, Pasar Liwa Village, Balik Bukit District, West Lampung Regency. Based on a letter from the Head of the Master of Education Administration Study Program at the University of Lampung Number: 617/UN26.13.PN.01.00/2023 dated September 18 2023, regarding research/observation permits. The research was carried out from January 20 2023 to February 25 2023, data collection was carried out at STP TK Khoiru Ummah. The following is the focus of the research carried out:

Table 1. Research Focus

No	Research Sub Focus	Data Indicator
1.	Planning	a. Planning a curriculum concept based on Islamic beliefs b. Preparation of Learning Tools (Education Calendar, annual program, Program holiday, Syllabus, lesson plan)
2.	Organizing	a. Preparation of organizational structure b. Division of duties and responsibilities of educators and education staff
3.	<i>Actuating</i>	a. Learning Activities b. Learning methods c. Synergy between schools and parents
4.	<i>Controlling</i>	a. Implementation of Supervision b. Utilization of supervision results to improve the quality of curriculum management based on Islamic beliefs

Curriculum Planning Based on Islamic Aqedah curriculum

Based on the presentation of data obtained from documentation studies, observations and interviews, curriculum management planning based on Islamic beliefs has been running well. Planning is the first management step needed to achieve organizational goals. Management is a field of science that understands why and how people work together to achieve set goals. Management is a process to achieve organizational goals that have been set by carrying out all management functions including planning, implementation and evaluation functions. Planning is carried out to determine overall goals and the best way to fulfill them or how to achieve these goals (Marsakha et al., 2021)

Based on the data obtained from observations and interviews, planning was carried out by the head of the foundation, the school principal, the person in charge of the curriculum, and the teachers to set goals which were then formulated by forming the school's vision, mission and goals. Education has a dual role and function to achieve the desired goals. When implementing education management, clear goals and objectives are needed to achieve process efficiency and work product effectiveness (Vidieyanti et al, 2022)

Learning planning is carried out by creating a modified academic calendar based on the Khoiru Ummah curriculum, creating a learning schedule according to the conditions of each school. The learning planning process for the Tahfizh Plus Khoiru School (STP) SDIT Khoiru Ummah Liwa is mature, because it looks very systematic in its implementation, runs regularly and is very organized. Meanwhile, the principles that must be considered in preparing plans are: (1) The formulation of competencies in teaching preparation must be clear. The more concrete a competency is, the easier it is to observe and the more precise the activities that must be carried out to form that competency. (2) Teaching arrangements must be simple and flexible and can be implemented in learning activities and the formation of student competencies. (3) Activities prepared and developed in preparation for teaching must support and be in accordance with the established competencies. (4) The teaching preparation developed must be complete and comprehensive, and its achievements must be clear. (5) There must be coordination between implementing components of the school program, especially if learning is carried out in team teaching or moving classes (Mulyasa, 2004).

Curriculum planning involves teachers, those in charge of the curriculum, school principals, foundations and educational experts. Through the roles of these various parties, it is hoped that each member of the organization can express ideas before the plan is finalized. Planning is related to decision making, vision and mission is a strategy for achieving goals and has an influence on

improving facilities, generating funds, ensuring the quality of educators and education personnel, measuring the strengths and weaknesses of the organization and is a preparation for facing problems that may occur (Rini, et al 2020)

Organizing a Curriculum Based on Islamic Faith.

Organizing requires leadership skills that are used in making decisions and being able to adapt to master organizational development. School principals need skills in management, planning, development, decision making and current developments. Thus, it can be said that the role of leadership has a dynamic relationship in work which is built starting from planning, organizing and implementation which is obtained by the collaboration of leaders and followers which has an influence on progress in education to provide guidance towards achieving organizational goals (Supriyadi et al. , 2023).

Organizing is carried out by the school principal together with the person in charge of the curriculum and in consultation with the competent leadership, this aims to give strength to each member of the organization who has a leading role to achieve educational goals at STP SDIT Khoiru Ummah Liwa West Lampung. Before starting the new school year, the school principal analyzes human resource needs by determining human resources who have the same vision and mission to achieve the goals or output of graduates from SDIT Khoiru Ummah Liwa School. Then the principal distributes tasks to all teachers and staff, related to the daily teaching and learning process. So that everyone has responsibility for what has been mandated.

Implementation of an Islamic Creed-Based Curriculum

Implementation is the steps on how to do it, what needs are needed, how to achieve the goals and it is clear who will achieve the results in the implementation according to the plans made. In implementing the academic program, the principal knows and together with members of the organization carries out all plans and policies that have been formulated and determined, equipped with all the requirements, tools needed, coordinating who is implementing it, where the implementation is and how to ensure the implementation is achieved.

The role of the principal is to collaborate with other parties to create leadership that can influence achieving targets, collaborate with teachers and become a colleague for teachers in implementing learning. In implementation, the school principal must be able to build positive relationships to increase teacher enthusiasm and commitment and build community support (Pebriantika et al., 2020). Implementation shows that the implementation of curriculum management based on Islamic beliefs is implemented by educators and education staff who are very aware of the vision, mission and objectives of the foundation and use it as a basis for compiling all activity programs. Clarity of vision, mission and goals is one of the stages in implementing learning. STP SDIT Khoiru Ummah Liwa West Lampung has a goal in education that the surrounding elementary schools do not have, namely the formation of students who have Islamic thought patterns and attitudes, are faqih fiddin, and are at the forefront of science. An educational institution must have a strategy to be trusted by the public, have internal processes that competitors do not have and can provide customer satisfaction. Through implementation that is in accordance with the vision and mission, an educational institution can be maintained (Dewi et al., 2016)

Implementation is the mobilization of members to carry out mutually agreed goals, this mobilization should be carried out by a manager. The manager who drives the implementation is not only the school principal but together with parties with more authority above him, namely the foundation, the foundation director, and the Curriculum quality guarantor. The mobilization function is the implementation of planning and organizing activities. The emphasis of the implementation function is on creating cooperation between members of the organization and increasing the work spirit of all members in order to achieve organizational goals (Amtu, 2013).

In implementing the Islamic creed-based curriculum, all subjects are integrated with Islamic creeds. This allows students not only to understand the relationship between one subject and another, but also between school knowledge and learning experiences outside of school, as well as between the curriculum and students' talents, interests and personal needs. Integration is built to highlight the horizontal relationships of various student learning experiences, both within one subject and between subjects, because learning will be more effective if the facts and principles of one subject or field of study are linked to the facts and principles of other subjects or fields of study. Through integration, educators show horizontal relationships between learning experiences so that students have a comprehensive, broader and deeper view, not only conceptually but also applying knowledge, skills and values in real life (Torang, 2016). Actual Learning in the Islamic Aqidah-Based Curriculum Based on the implementation of Islamic Aqidah-based learning at

STP Khoiru Ummah using the discovery learning method, or learning by doing, or usually called the Talqiyyan Fikriyyan strategy because the addition of the Talqiyyan Fikriyyan method is a learning by doing strategy that is integrated with Islamic creeds, and The learning media used is in accordance with the theme being studied. The concept of learning is actually similar to the idea of learning by doing which was initiated by an educational figure, John Dewey. This concept emphasizes the importance of learning something while practicing it directly (Haenilah, 2015).

Factors that influence the achievement of learning goals are teachers and parents. It is important to unite perceptions and knowledge about children in a comprehensive and detailed manner, teachers and parents must collaborate. Therefore, through an Islamic Creed-based curriculum, students will gain knowledge based on direct experience based on aspects of faith or obedience. If the elements of Islamic faith are supported by morals or personality that are in accordance with Islamic law, then it is very appropriate for religious education to enter the inner and outer self of students who are formed at home and strengthened at school. The religion-based character education model implemented by Islamic schools shows that all components or the school community, including parents, carry out religion-based character education, so that it becomes a real example for all students (Cinantya et al., 2018).

The entire process of implementing an Islamic faith-based curriculum is to achieve Khoiru ummah's vision of becoming a representative of an Islamic Aqidah-based educational institution, which is at the forefront of producing a generation of leaders of a noble civilization (Islam). Therefore, the concept of education based on Islamic beliefs must be socialized to all parents, teachers and the community to work together to create the best generation of the Ummah with morals or noble character.

Supervision of Islamic Creed-Based Curriculum

Supervision of curriculum management based on Islamic beliefs is carried out by the school principal by holding regular meetings to evaluate appropriate and inappropriate plans and then use them as material for further improvements which are useful for maintaining the quality of education which should be the main task of the school principal. Supervision is carried out with mutual trust among members of the organization, each member has responsibility for their respective duties and is given the opportunity to work according to their competencies.

Every member of the company must think positively and be trusted to have better decision-making and problem-solving abilities and sharpen skills. Quality is realized by a group of trained members and needs to have a sense of volunteerism from members. Teamwork is really needed to maintain quality (Rafaai. Z et al., 2018)

School principals are also supported by always improving the quality of human resources and collaborating with other experts. In this case, STP SDIT Khoiru Ummah Liwa West Lampung is collaborating with the Umami Foundation in improving the competency of teaching the Al-Qur'an, which is the core curriculum in curriculum management based on Islamic beliefs. Organizational groups with few members are very effective in increasing awareness of building and improving quality, improving teamwork and process efficiency, and achieving customer satisfaction as an organizational advantage. Problems are resolved through discussion, brainstorming and mutual trust. This can hone members to be introspective and think critically. Quality defense is also supported by effectiveness in establishing collaboration with other companies (Baisalim.M.F et al., 2022).

STP SDIT Khoiru Ummah Liwa also routinely provides monthly school progress reports to the central Khoiru Ummah. This is a form of communication that is always established for the monitoring process to ensure the quality of learning in schools. Communication is an activity that is always carried out by everyone wherever they are, because communication is one of the needs of humans as social creatures. Even though communication can be said to be the heart of life in an organization, without communication the organization will die, at least it will not be able to develop optimally because communication is the key to successful team efficiency (Suriansyah, 2014). The supervision or control stage can influence the future management planning process, because carrying out supervision means carrying out evaluations in the field to identify weaknesses and errors that occur in order to be corrected in implementation. Therefore, supervision must be carried out as well as possible so that the goals achieved can be realized. Supervision is a systematic effort to establish implementation standards with the aim of planning, designing a feedback information system, comparing actual activities with standards, determining and measuring deviations and taking corrective action to ensure that all available resources are used effectively and efficiently.

4. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of research and discussions conducted by researchers on Islamic faith-based management at STP SDIT Khoiru Ummah Liwa West Lampung, it can be concluded that:

Planning of Islamic Aqidah-based curriculum

Planning for implementing Islamic faith-based curriculum management is designed in accordance with the vision of the school's mission. Implementation of the Islamic faith-based curriculum is carried out by creating learning tools such as creating a modified academic calendar based on the central Khoiru Ummah curriculum, creating learning schedules according to the conditions of each school.

Organizing an Islamic Aqidah-based curriculum

The organization for implementing this curriculum is that each school has a different organizational structure, which then details the school principal distributing tasks to all educators and education staff for implementing daily learning.

Implementation of an Islamic Aqidah-based curriculum

Implementation of learning using is carried out in five days. The learning method is carried out using the "talqiyyan fikriyyan" method by integrating all knowledge into the Islamic faith. Factors that influence the implementation of this curriculum are parents, society and the government, so that parenting programs are implemented to equalize perceptions between schools and parents to achieve a curriculum based on Islamic beliefs.

Supervision of the Islamic Aqidah-based curriculum

The form of supervision they carry out is a form of internal control or control carried out by the leadership and leadership of the foundation, either directly or indirectly. The school also schedules regular meetings for teachers and foundation administrators to find out about developments and obstacles that occur in the field and then look for joint solutions as a follow-up to improvements in the next implementation.

Limitations and further studies

Future researchers are expected to study in more depth research on curriculum management based on Islamic beliefs. Because this research is limited to the scope of one school only. It is hoped that future researchers will be able to perfect this research in the context of comparing research findings with Islamic faith-based curriculum management theory with deeper and sharper academic quality, so that the results of future researchers will be even better.

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